

**Study of the genus *Anthrenus* subgenus *Anthrenodes*. Part 3.
Two new species from Yemen
(Coleoptera, Dermestidae, Megatominae)**

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Key words: Taxonomy, new species, description, Coleoptera, Dermestidae, *Anthrenus*, *Anthrenodes*, Yemen.

Abstract: The following species from Yemen are described, illustrated and compared with similar species: *Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) haladai* **sp. nov.**, *Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) maribensis* **sp. nov.** A list of species recorded from Yemen is added.

Introduction

The subgenus *Anthrenodes* Chobaut, 1898 of the genus *Anthrenus* Geoffroy, 1762 currently contains 36 species worldwide (Háva 2024a, b) and only three species are known from the Yemen including Socotra Island (Háva 2017, 2024a).

The subgenus is characterized by antennae consisting of 10 antennomeres. Males differ from females by the shape of the antennal club. In males, the terminal antennomere is larger or longer than the penultimate one; in females it is as long as the penultimate one. Adults can be found on plants, but also in households, where the larvae are harmful to different commodities of natural origin. They are feared pests in museum collections (Peacock, 1993; Háva 2024b). Two new species are described below.

Material and methods

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

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TL: total length - linear distance from anterior margin of pronotum to apex of elytra.

EW: elytral width - maximum linear transverse distance.

The material mentioned is deposited in (JHAC) - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic.

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed label with text as follows:

„HOLOTYPE [or PARATYPE] *species name* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2024”.

Results

Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) haladai sp. nov.

Figs 1-4

Description. Male. Body TL 3.0 mm, EW 2.3 mm; body brown, small, oval. Dorsal surface covered by brown, yellow and white scales. Individual scales small, broad, subtriangular.

Head covered by intermixed yellow and white scales. Antennae with 10 antennomeres, antennomeres I-VIII brown, IX-X dark brown, antennal club with 3 antennomeres, compact (Fig. 2). Frons with median ocellus. Eyes with entire median margin. Palpomeres brownish-black.

Pronotum covered with intermixed white and yellow scales laterally, with brown scales centrally on disc (Fig. 1).

Scutellum small, triangular without scales.

Elytra with brown, yellow and white scales; brown scales forming spots on each elytron, other parts covered by intermixed white and yellow scales. Epipleuron with white scales.

Ventral surface covered with white scales. Prosternum only with white scales. Metasternum only with white scales. Abdominal ventrites I-V without spots on the middle and antero-lateral margins, covered with only white scales (Fig. 4).

Legs brown with white scales and white setae.

Male aedeagus very small, median lobe slightly curved (Fig. 3).

Female. Unknown.

Figs. 1-4. *Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) haladai* sp. nov.: 1 - body, dorsal aspect; 2 - antenna; 3 - male genitalia; 4 - abdomen.

Figs. 5-8. *Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) maribensis* sp. nov.: 5 - body, dorsal aspect; 6 - antenna; 7 - male genitalia; 8 - abdomen.

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Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from *A. hulai* Háva, 2017 by the form of the body, dorsal colouration and ventral scales (*A. hulai* - dorsal surface covered with grey and brown scales, ventral side mainly with grey scales) and the structure of the antennae and male genitalia; the same characters found in the other Yemeni species.

Type material. Holotype (♂): S Yemen, Lawdar NE, Adan, 13°53'N, 45°48' E, 1145 m, 22.10.2005, P. Kabátek lgt. - JHAC.

Etymology. Patronymic, dedicated to the Czech entomologist, specialist in Hymenoptera, Jiří Halada (Czech Republic).

Anthrenus (Anthrenodes) maribensis sp. nov.

Figs 5-8

Description. Males. Body TL 1.7-1.8 mm, EW 1.1-1.2 mm; head, pronotum dark brown, elytra brown, small, oval. Dorsal surface covered with white scales. Individual scales small, broad, subtriangular.

Head covered with white scales. Antennae with 10 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, antennal club with 3 antennomeres, compact (Fig. 6). Frons with median ocellus. Eyes with entire median margin. Palpomeres brown.

Pronotum covered with white scales (Fig. 5).

Scutellum small, triangular without scales.

Elytra with white scales. Epipleuron with white scales.

Ventral surface covered with white scales. Prosternum only with white scales. Metasternum only with white scales. Abdominal ventrites I-V without spots in the middle and antero-lateral margins, covered with only white scales (Fig. 8).

Legs brown with white scales and white setae.

Male aedeagus (Fig. 7).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from *A. malkini* Mroczkowski, 1980 and *A. pulchellus* Gestro, 1889 by the very small body form, the body covered only with white scales and the structure of the antennae and male genitalia; the same characters found in the other Yemeni species.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Yemen N, Wadi Sudd, 10 km W Marib, 15°24'N, 45°16'E, 1120 m, 8.10.2005, J. Halada lgt. - JHAC.

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Paratype (1 ♂): same data as holotype - JHAC.

Etymology. Toponymic, named for Marib city, where the holotype was collected.

List of *Anthrenodes* species recorded from Yemen

A. haladai **sp. nov.**

A. hulai Háva, 2017

A. malkini Mroczkowski, 1980

A. maribensis **sp. nov.**

A. pulchellus Gestro, 1889

Acknowledgements. I would like to thank to Petr Kabátek and Jiří Halada (both Czech Republic) for providing me the interesting material and to Larry G. Bezark (California, U.S.A.) for a revision of the English manuscript.

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Received: 10.09.2024

Accepted: 20.10.2024